

RESEARCH STUDY

RECOMMENDATIONS

**ON PUBLIC POLICIES, REGULATIONS/
AMENDMENTS**

FOR THE RELEVANT PUBLIC AUTHORITIES

FROM THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

Chisinau, 2015

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Authors:

RNDr. Vratislav Datel - Expert, Czech Republic

dr. Krzysztof Atlasiewicz - Expert, Poland

Vladimir Benko - Expert, Slovakia

Ion Coșuleanu - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chișinău

dr. hab. Anatol Gremalschi – [Institute for Public Policy](#), Chișinău

Editorial team:

Irina Cojocaru - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chișinău

dr. Elena Ungureanu - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chișinău

Anastasia Ștefanița - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chișinău

Dumitra Ungureanu - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chișinău

dr. Igor Cojocaru - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chișinău

Cristina Antoci - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chișinău

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Abbreviations

ATU	administrative-territorial units
BPMN	Business Process Modelling Notation - a method of illustrating business processes in the form of a diagram similar to a flowchart.
BR	Basic Registries
CPA	Central Public Authority
DISCUS	Discussion on Information Society Building Issues Platform
DS	De-concentrated Services
EDIFACT	Electronic Data Interchange For Administration Commerce and Transport
EGON	System of the Shared Services in the Czech Republic
GNP	Gross National Product
ICT	Information & Communication Technologies
IRI	International Republican Institute
IS	Information System
ISDI/IDSI	Information Society Development Institute, Moldova
ISPA	Information System of Public Administration in Czech Republic
KIO	National Appeal Chamber, Poland
LPA	Local Public Authorities
OPSI	Office for Public Information Systems
PA	Public Administration
PIAPs	Public Internet Access Points
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
PRINCE2	Projects In a Controlled Environment is a project management method based on a process approach
PuP	Public-public partnership is a partnership between government administration or other public authority or other body
SOA	Service Oriented Infrastructure
V4	Visegrad countries: Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia

1. Introduction

The research study “**Recommendations on public policies, regulations/ amendments for the relevant public authorities**” is written within the DISCUS project as the result of the scientific seminar: **ICT solutions for local services (legal regulations)** and is a continuation of the research study “**Recommendation on implementation of relevant IS for local authorities**”.

The **main goal** of the Seminar was to share the experience of Visegrad countries in the field of information society with a focus on legal regulations in the field of electronic services, including local services and taking into consideration V4 best practices in this area by the Moldavian officials, researchers and national policy makers. The **objective of the seminar** was to discuss the problems and identify possible solutions regarding legal regulations for local electronic services in Moldova.

The seminar held on May 26-27 (Agenda provided in the Annex 4) in Chisinau, brought about the valuable input information from representatives of local and central public authorities of Moldova on the one hand, and from the V4 countries experts on the other hand. The event was attended by specialists in various areas: local public servants, representatives of academic sector, central government, civil society, national experts and international experts from Visegrad countries (for more detailed information see Annex 3).

The information gathered from representatives of the local authorities during the first project event held in March 2015 served as a basis for the Seminar agenda.

The participants to the Seminar pinpointed a range of issues in implementation of e-services on local level, such as:

- lack of information campaigns for the citizens and of training for civil servants in rural area;
- documents duplication;
- lack of pilot projects from the central level to raion - and from raion to cities/villages, which could be undertaken for multiplication in other localities;
- resistance to change;
- lack of experts group to consult and support local authorities in e-services implementation;
- lack of partnership network (central government, local administration, civil society, business etc.)

The materials of the research study are sometimes beyond the Seminar discussions, to provide additional information on EU, V4 countries experience, as well as on the state of the art on discussed issues in the Republic of Moldova.

In the State of the Art chapter, the information on the Republic of Moldova administrative structure is provided in order to help V4 experts to deliver more focused recommendations to actions to be undertaken by the country, in transposition of the EU and V4 countries experience.

A special chapter is devoted to Visegrad countries experience on ICT solutions for local services (with a focus on experience in legal regulations field) and best practices relevant to be approached by Moldova .

The chapter on Lessons learnt provides ICT solutions for local services, focused on the experience of the Czech Republic, Slovakia and Poland in legal regulations field.

Based on the Findings of the scientific seminar, as well as Czech Republic, Slovakia and Poland experience, recommendations on public policies, regulations to be developed or amended for/by the relevant public authorities from Moldova are formulated.

The Study provides the main steps to be included into the Action plan for implementation of local e-services in rural localities and the recommendations and suggestions for the next DISCUS event: Workshop from September 22-23, Chisinau.

2. State of the art - Republic of Moldova (with a focus on legal regulations)

In the Republic of Moldova the main necessary legislative and normative framework for building information society was created. It currently includes more than 20 laws, 80 Government decisions, about 70 approved conceptual documents regarding the information systems of public authorities, more than 20 general purpose regulatory acts and 75 with a specific purpose issued by ANRCETI.

The legal regulations in the Republic of Moldova that make up the framework for providing public services, including online services, consist of a range of laws, Government Decisions, regulations and local acts. The relevant institutional framework is in place, it includes the Ministry of Information Technology and Communications, the National Regulatory Agency for Electronic Communications and Information Technology (ANRCETI), National Radio Frequency Centre, Centre for Electronic Governance and National Centre for Personal Data Protection.

A list of the main normative acts is provided in the Annex 1.

For a more clear understanding of the framework for providing services by local public authorities, below is given a brief description of public administration in the country.

1. System of local public administration

In accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Moldova, public administration in the administrative/territorial units is based on the principles of local autonomy, decentralization of public services, eligibility of local public administration authorities and on consultation of the citizens on local problems of special interest. The Law on Local Public Administration defines local public administration as a totality of local public authorities, created within the law, to meet general interests of the residents of a certain territorial administrative unit. The system of local public administration consists of two levels:

The first level - public bodies with general or special powers, created and functioning on the territory of a village or town/municipality, with the purpose of promoting the interests of the local community and resolving its problems.

The second level - public bodies with general or special powers, created and functioning on the territory of raions (districts), Chisinau municipality and the special legal-status autonomous territorial unit, with the purpose of promoting the interests and resolving the problems of the population of the given territorial administrative unit.

2. The region: definition and context

The Republic of Moldova is divided into villages, cities, raions (districts) and the autonomous territorial unit of Gagauzia and territorial unit Stinga Nistrului (Transdnistria). There are 32 raions, 3 municipalities, and 2 autonomous territorial units. Gagauzia is a region with the predominantly Christian-Orthodox population speaking a Turkish dialect. It is governed by Moldovan laws, as well as normative acts issued by the Gagauzian Parliament. Gagauzia has the right to independently determine issues relating to its political, economic and cultural development. Although Transdnistria is formally and internationally considered to be a part of Moldova, the Moldovan authorities do not exercise any control over this breakaway region.

According to the Decentralization Strategy, there are 3 development regions: North, Centre and South Development Regions. They don't have any formally given public administrative powers and are oriented to implementation of development projects, which cover more than 1 raion.

3. Institutional Organization

Each raion (district) elects a council which co-ordinates the activities of the local councils, in order to provide public services on district or municipal level. The councils are elected on the basis of universal, equal and direct suffrage by secret ballot for a term of four years.

The relations between the central and local public administration can be called supervision. The State Chancellery is responsible for the organization of the administrative control of the legality of the activity of the local public administration authorities, exercised by its own agencies or via subordinated territorial offices.

There is a doubtful status of the services in second-level LPAs' responsibility and the confusion between those and the deconcentrated services. The administrative legislation and practice of the Republic of Moldova does not establish clearly, which are the fundamental differences between the decentralized services, the deconcentrated and delegated ones. There is a tendency amongst several CPA's institutions to consider, in practice, the district decentralized services/institutions as being deconcentrated services/institutions, in respect of which they can influence and exercise directly and voluntarily their managing authority. Moreover, different reports analysing the general condition in the public sector of the Republic of Moldova underline the exaggerated growth of such, especially regarding the public expenditures in the Gross National Product (further – GNP) in comparison with the level of development measured by the GNP/resident index, and suggest the restriction of its expansion. This factor has a special influence on the decentralization process, because of the extreme restriction of the fiscal space necessary for a better financing of the LPA.

4. Competences

The Law on Local Public Administration defines own and delegated powers of the districts. Responsibilities of the districts include: (i) social, economic, territorial and urban development; (ii) construction of raion roads, construction of public facilities in the raion (district); (iii) lyceum-type educational institutions except those rendering to the first level; (iv) provision of social assistance; (v) sports and other activities; (vi) protection of environment; (vii) management of property; (viii) fire protection services, etc.

There is a wide range of responsibilities delegated to the districts by the state, including social protection, health care, public safety, natural reservations etc, In these areas, in accordance

with the law, the local authorities are subject to administrative supervision with the regard to expediency.

First of all, de jure, the LPA authorities in the Republic of Moldova have an autonomy declaratively full, but, de facto, this is limited, in part because of the CPA's interference

in their daily activity, in part due to the fact that their own financial resources do not reach the limit of needs, the lack of which is accompanied by an excessively fragmented territorial-administrative organization, and in part because of the insufficient administrative and institutional capacity. These conditions make the LPA to present a low degree of responsabilization in front of the public – the public representing the main beneficiary and decision-taking body, when it handles with the use of the resources and the adaptation of public service to the local needs. The delimitation of the competences amongst the first and second level LPAs is unclear, contradictory, and in some cases even lacking. Some of the activities mentioned as in-house competences haven't been clearly defined, in some cases these being attributed to the tasks of the immediately upper level.

This situation allows the double, equivocal interpretation of the responsibilities/competences of different levels of administrative-territorial units (further – ATU). There're no clear and functional technical criteria which would be enacted and used expressly for the competences' definition, delimitation, assurance and financing.

The responsibilities/competences' doubling phenomenon is present in the activity of deconcentrated specialized public authorities as well. Accordingly, the lack of a clear competences' delimitation tends to put pressure, destabilize the whole system of inter-administrative relationships.¹

5. Financing

The Law on Local Public Administration states that local public administration bodies enjoy financial autonomy and are entitled to initiative in all issues related to the administration of local public affairs. According to the Law on Local Public Finance the raion budget includes: (i) revenues and expenses needed to fulfil responsibilities assigned to the raion according to the law and the additional responsibilities delegated to the Government; (ii) the local budgets which consist of the budgets of the villages (communes), cities (municipalities) within the raion. Local budgets may impose local taxes and charges in the limits determined by the law. The national government estimates the share of the consolidated national budget, which may be spent for financing the public services provided by local authorities (both own and delegated responsibilities).

In the Republic of Moldova, just like in many other transition countries, the decentralization of certain public services and the transfer of some of the responsibilities/competences, has not been fulfilled in line with the transfer of the resources that are necessary for their fulfilment, which lead to the emergence of some deep vertical disequilibrium in the financing. As a result, the exercise of these attributions is difficult and sometimes even impossible for the small ATUs or those having a poor budget. At present, insufficient financial resources to cover public spending is due to the inefficient tax collection and local taxes, which does not allow LPA to accumulate sufficient financial resources to stimulate community development and public expenses. There are no viable mechanisms that would allow the expansion of the fiscal base of the administrative territorial units. These issues contribute indirectly to the situation where mayors and local councillors, to get financial support, exhibit loyalty without

¹http://eap-csf.eu/assets/files/Downloads/english/Draft_National_Decentralization_Strategy_eng.pdf

reservation with respect to governing political superiors, and this process greatly undermines local government act.²

At the same time, a mechanism that would guarantee the ATUs' necessary medium and long-term financial resources for the fulfilment of the responsibilities/competences transferred by the state, is necessary to be established. The experts recommend to revise the concept of local budgets, turning them into independent budgets of local authorities at both levels, that they have adequate own revenue according to their competencies, while being empowered to amend budgets within the law limits.³

6. The State and the regions

In accordance with the legislation, the activity of the first and second level local public authorities is subject to an administrative control. The Law on Local Public Administration provides a list of items, which are subject to the obligatory supervision of the Government and State Chancellery. The administration control includes the control of the legislation and the adequacy of the politics of public administration authorities.

7. The regions and local authorities

The Constitution of Moldova, as well as the Law on Local Public Administration claims that interrelationships of public authorities are based on the principles of autonomy, legality, transparency and co-operation in solving common problems.

8. The regions and international relations

According to the Law on Local Public Administration the raion (district) councils may decide within the law, to cooperate with other authorities of the local public administration, including cross-border cooperation, for the implementation of activities and rendering necessary public services, as well as the cooperation with national and foreign economic entities and non-governmental organizations in view of realization of activities or works of common interests.

9. Conclusions

There is an evident lack of financial and administrative autonomy for regional authorities in Moldova, which are limited in decision-making powers regarding their own administrative structure and bound some very heavy delegated responsibilities and are thus more dependent than ever before on the central authorities. Distribution of responsibilities between two different levels of public power is, in fact, a system of diffusion of power, rather than proper decentralization.⁴

10. Actions undertaken:

10.1. Public Services Reform Program

² Liubomir Chiriac, Victor Mocanu, Angela Secieru, Gheorghe Gladchi "Conflictul de interese și regimul de incompatibilități în instituțiile administrației publice locale din Republica Moldova", 2012, Fundația SOROS Moldova, (<http://www.viitorul.org/doc.php?l=ro&idc=306&id=3966&t=/STUDII-IDIS/Administrare-publica/>)

³ Ion Creangă, Irina Gălușcă Noile reglementări ale procesului bugetar pentru APL Principii Reguli Responsabilități. Biblioteca IDIS „Viitorul”

⁴ http://www.aer.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/MainIssues/Regional_Democracy/AER_Regionalism_Report/Report_by_country/MOLDOVA_2010.pdf

According to Public Services Reform Program approved by the Government⁵, re-engineering of public services is one of the most urgent priorities of the Government of Moldova, but also a major challenge that requires rethinking and transforming traditional patterns of activity of public authorities and institutions. The vertically organized public institutions that operate within the strict limits of the powers set by normative acts, are to be restructured into a single system that will remove institutional barriers, will develop horizontal linkages and cooperation instruments that provide efficient organization of public services for citizens and entrepreneurs and economical use of resources of central and local public authorities. This is necessary due to the rapid development of technological innovations, as well as the increasing demands of society. The project on public services modernization, developed by the European Commission, states: "Today citizens know their rights better and better, have more information about public services and therefore have higher expectations and requirements to the quality of services"⁶

The Program identified two main groups of issues related to public service reform.

The first group aimed at service system itself, covering such issues as quality of service, accessibility of information on services, the time required to obtain a specific service, the possibility to choose the channels for offering service to beneficiaries, respecting rule of law in the provision of services, reasonable costs for citizens and businesses, service culture, ensuring service delivery infrastructure, organization of economically efficient services .

A second group of issues relates to public service reform itself and covers such issues as quality of reform policies by setting clear goals, principles and policy tools, activities and measures planned, correctness and their consistency with other government initiatives, primarily with e-transformation agenda, providing resources, establishing effective mechanisms for reform coordination and management, awareness by civil servants both at management level, and at the level of experts on essence and complexity of reform.

Generalization of the existing problems from the beneficiaries' perspective includes:

1) incomplete information posted on the public institutions websites. In most cases to benefit from the necessary service, recipients are forced to visit in person the servicing institutions.

According to survey results, in 2013 - more than 50% beneficiaries have recognized that the information on the website about the required service was insufficient.

2) narrow institutional approach and isolation of public institutions in organizing services. The beneficiary continues to act as a courier, ensuring the exchange of documents between public institutions. Although the interoperability of public registers is being implemented, it works only in isolated cases, requiring significant time and additional economic costs to citizens and businesses.

According to 2013 survey results - to get a distinct service, more than 30% of beneficiaries had to visit more than 3 institutions.

⁵ Hotărârea Guvernului nr.122 din 18 februarie 2014

⁶ <http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/vision-public-services>.

3) Lack of systematic procedures and practices to assess the administrative burden. The regulatory framework, which sets out the procedure for obtaining service provides requirements that might yield without additional risks, but systematic assessment and identification of excessive existing procedures and processes are carried out only in separate cases, particularly in international technical assistance projects.

4) **Arbitrary inclusion of additional requirements beyond of normative acts provisions (laws, government decisions, decisions by local authorities) established by the institutions' internal instructions on the service.** This requires the need for repeated visits to institutions to submit documents not covered by legal acts and not included in the lists of documents posted on institutions' websites. This way the time needed to get a service is increasing.

5) Lack of uniform and transparent principles for establishing tariffs for paid services. Prices for services are perceived by most people as arbitrary or unreasonable.

According to the survey results in 2013 - more than 58% of beneficiaries considered the tariffs for services as unjustified.

6) The existence of unofficial supplementary payments claimed by beneficiaries. The 2011 Survey, conducted by the International Republican Institute (IRI), Baltic Surveys / The Gallup Organization, showed that additional informal payments constituted the usual way of solving the problems of citizens interacting with public institutions in more than 80% of cases. According to the 2013 Survey, 47% of respondents admitted that unofficial payments were requested in the delivery of a service.

The Public Service Reform Program identified the following problems in implementing the civil service reform:

1) **The absence of a clear definition of public services** and public service diversity in legislation. The general concept of public service is used as a synonym for administrative public service, services for public benefit etc., leading to confusion in defining reform subject and unclear planning of modernization objectives.

2) The absence of legal framework for the reform. There are no definitions in the law of many concepts and basic procedures related to public service reform. Such concepts as holder of public service and public service providers, front-office and back-office concept developed under European and international best practices, the processes of service etc., are used intuitively, which complicates the reform implementation - different institutions involved in the reform understand differently what should be achieved and by what methods and activities.

3) Institutional isolation. **Public administration are considering services from their point of view, and not from the perspective of beneficiaries**, for which the institutional barriers of government creates an additional administrative burden. A view at the range of services in terms of beneficiaries, horizontal analysis and modernization initiatives of groups of services according to the principle of "life situations", in line with European and international good practices is carried out only in isolated cases, with the support of international technical assistance projects.

4) Duplication of the methodological studies. **The absence of unified approved guidelines on analysis and services reengineering** leads to repeated efforts of institutions to create

distinct methodologies in technical assistance projects, which involve irrational use of resources and gaps in addressing the reform.

5) ***Lack of principles and modalities for setting tariffs on paid services*** tends to lead to higher fares, paid services are perceived as a source of additional revenue for public institutions to their budget. On the other hand, the messy legislative framework makes it difficult to counter all elements of service costs in price calculation, as well as the objective assessment of the proposed tariffs.

6) ***The absence of a uniform approach to public service reform affects the definition of service standards***. There are several ways to define the minimum standards and requirements for the quality of public services, but overall the quality monitoring is carried out sporadically, case by case, which makes it difficult to assess the dynamics of changes made to improve services.

7) ***The absence of a common understanding of the principle of "single window"***. Despite the widespread use of the name "single window", in reality there are different approaches to the implementation of the model of "one-stop shop" in providing services. There are cases when the implementation of "single window" is expressed by organizing a series of simultaneous "one-stop shops" in the same establishment or organization under the aegis of "single window" one-stop shop leads for beneficiaries visiting 10 times the establishment, in fact degraded this principle.

The principle of "single window" is understandable, yet only as a mechanism to streamline business activity, in that it is governed by Law 161 of 22 July 2011 on the implementation of one-stop shop for entrepreneurial activity. Examples of implemented one-stop shop so far for public authorities are very few. Thus, there remains the issue regarding the definition, the principle that the whole system of public services and the establishment of one-stop shop in procedure, provide other public services, not only those services related to the permissive acts issuance.

8) Lack of resources and coordination mechanism for the public services reform. The coordination and surveillance of reforming public services common to all public authorities and institutions, is the competence of the State Chancellery, but there is no appropriate consultative mechanism established. There is a lack of network of responsible specialists from relevant ministries and there are not designated human resources to manage the reform. Compared with the activities coordinated by the Centre for Electronic Governance, overall coordination of the civil service reform is extremely weak. The existing resources are insufficient for developing and implementing legislative amendments, training of specialists from ministries, development of methodological guidelines for the reform of public services, for good planning and monitoring of the reform. This lack of coordination mechanisms for the main direction of public service reform and initiatives is affecting services digitization initiatives, the efficient use of information technologies, actually representing the second phase of modernization services, which provides that services are already in place, assessed, and processes and excessive requirements are excluded, i.e. services reengineering process is performed.

The general objective of the Reform Program is reforming public services in the Republic of Moldova in public authorities both central and local, to ensure the provision of high quality, fast, accessible, transparent and efficient services, in terms of cost for a increasing number of citizens.

The general objective of the Programme is to focus on ensuring the interests of society and service users.

As result indicators for the general objective, the following performance indicators (PIs) from the beneficiary's perspective:

PI 1: Reduce the time required to obtain information about services and service outcome.

PI 2: Reduce the number of visits to institutions to receive services.

PI 3: Reduce the distance to the provision of services.

PI 4: Reduce the cost of services for beneficiaries.

PI 5: Improve quality of service (satisfaction of beneficiaries).

PI 6: Reduce the number of complaints.

Specific objective 1. Ensure a coordinated and unified approach to improving public services and the implementation of the strategic program of technological modernization of governance (e-Transformation).

Outcome 1: normative and methodological framework for reforming public services, ensuring efficient management and coordination of reform.

PI 7: Preparation and approval of the law on public services.

Target for 2015: Draft law on public services developed, consulted with public institutions, central and local public authorities and non-governmental organizations, approved by the Government and presented to the Parliament.

PI 8: Draft Government decisions and methodologies on the implementation of civil service reform developed

Target for 2015: The set of laws and methodologies developed, consulted and duly approved.

Specific objective 2. Reengineering and modernization of public services through digitization.

Outcome 2: Increasing efficiency and effectiveness in terms of cost for public services, including those provided on-line (e).

PI 9: The number of active Web pages, application models, documents necessary to receive service available on-line, technical facilities that allow online applications integrated into the portal of public services www.servicii.gov.md .

Target for 2015: active web pages for all public services and forms that can be downloaded on-line - 30%.

PI 10: The share of public services subject of reengineering in accordance with the Methodology

2014: 10%; 2015: 30%; 2016: 50%.

PI 11: Share of approved administrative regulations for public services after their reengineering

2014: 10%; 2015: 30%; 2016: 50%.

As can be seen, the Program objectives are oriented to on-line services, including those offered by local public administrations.

The National Action Plan for the implementation of the RM-EU Association Agreement 2014-2016, approved by Government Decision on 25 June 2014 is one of the most important documents in approximation of the legal framework on Information Society and ICT based services, to those of EU. The progress in implementation of this plan could substantially help in implementation of ICT based services at local level.

The most recent published policy document relevant to ICT based public services development is the Government of Moldova Activity Program 2015-2018⁷ (excerpts from the document in the Annex 5). The document inter alia provides for actions in adjustment of the normative-legal base for implementing government Interoperability Framework and of recommendations on interconnection and interoperability, as well as for implementation of access to registers and databases of national importance for all central and **local public authorities and institutions**, in accordance with the duties and functions of these authorities.

Practical steps have been undertaken in finding most relevant solutions for implementation of ICT based services at local level including with the support of development partners. The UNDP Joint Integrated Local Development Programme (JILDP) which promoted and implemented locally e-government system by research and implementation of e-services in 30 JILDP target communities⁸ and USAID Local Government Support Project (LGSP) that developed the Concept of Citizen Information and Service Center (CISC)⁹.

The Concept was developed under a pilot project for modernizing the activity of local public authorities in the Republic of Moldova, based on the example of one LPA. Depending on the results obtained in the respective pilot project implementation, this Concept can be easily replicated in other local public administration authorities.

Before bringing all services under the roof of CISC, the processes for providing the latter must be improved through remodeling, if needed. The remodeling process involves organization of workshops with the participation of representatives from the DS, ministries, and other actors involved in the service provision, identification of proposals for improving the current processes, using ICT solutions, as well as closer collaboration between DSs, LPAs, and other stakeholders involved in the service provision process. Some remodeling solutions require legislative amendments to be promoted, which may last a longer timeframe. Other operational solutions can be implemented in the short/immediate run, such as:

- Preparation of service provision related information and its posting on the LPA webpage, billboard, and publication in local mass media;
- LPA connection to the databases of State Enterprise Cadastru, State Enterprise CRIS Registru, etc.;

⁷ <http://www.parlament.md/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=uskJCCIZKz%3D&tabid=128&mid=506&language=ro-RO>

⁸ http://www.md.undp.org/content/moldova/en/home/operations/projects/poverty_reduction/joint-integrated-local-development-programme.html

⁹ http://descentralizare.gov.md/public/files/CIPS_Concept_paper_final_eng.pdf

- In the incipient phase – including in the documents’ circulation the scanned electronic versions of documents and organizing the work mainly in electronic form in order for the original documents to reach the file only by the end of the procedures.
- Receiving requests for documents and intermediary services in a single point, at CISC, and consecutively engaging the CISC to contact the de-concentrated authorities to respond to the requests received on behalf of the applicants.
- Carrying out random visits and controls based on risk criteria with the intention to get mainly in-officio approvals (if the information provided allows this). Implementing a single point for payment for public services, as well as a system for providing all the information related costs and payments in the process of authorization.

The key duties of the CISC include improving the services provided by LPA and providing information to physical and legal entities. In this sense, CISC represents the main tool for accomplishing the objectives of the latter, the overall goal of which will be to provide good quality services in a prompt manner, upon submission of a minimum set of documents.

CISC, in its quality of LPA Front Office, will be used for providing all the existing public services currently provided by the LPA. Taking into account the fact that improving the efficiency of services is an on-going process, the services provided through CISC will be of different maturity level, as mentioned bellow, while the mayor’s office staff will strive to develop the services and bring them to the highest level:

1. Information – Publication and dissemination of information. All the service provision related information will be published on the mayor’s office webpage, and will be also made available through the guidelines issued and disseminated by CISC.
2. Interaction – The citizens will have the possibility to contact the mayor’s office and deconcentrated services through the web-page or upload template application forms and documents.
3. Transaction – The citizens will have the possibility to carry out full transactions in electronic form. For example, the possibility to file a request and related documents in electronic form without involving the applicant in the process of obtaining a permissive document. In the case of CISC, the service is considered to be a transaction when the applicants file a request at the CISC, while the whole circuit of document, access to information, and coordination with other authorities involved is ensured electronically and is transparent for the applicants.
4. Transformation – The public authorities transform the current operational process to provide more efficient, integrated, unified, and customized services. This level represents an integration of internal and external institutions and systems to insure full communication between the public authorities. In the case of CISC, a service is considered to be at the level of transformation when it is eliminated through exchange of information between the authorities.

CISC will fulfill its duties by accomplishing their goals, mission, and tasks in 2 (two) consecutive stages:

- i) Preparation stage, which will involve creation of CISC, as a unit, approval of Internal Regulation, appointment of the Consultation Commission members, approval of the list of services provided by LPA, and of respective guidelines and regulations, as well as launching the CISC activity in an office designed for such purpose;
- ii) Implementation stage, which will include procurement of software and hardware, required

for CISC activity, staff training, piloting and starting full operation of CISC from organizational, operational and ICT points of view.

In the 2nd stage, after the implementation of the Electronic Registry of Local Services (ERLS) and of the System for Issuing Permissive Documents (SIPD), provided by Government through the e-Government Center (which will serve as a basis for the integrated information system of the mayor's office), the management and circulation of documents will take place in electronic form.

These systems will cover the entire circulation cycle of documents and information, starting with filing requests for obtaining services, for service provision, documents' circulation both within the mayor's office and de-concentrated services through communication and information exchange, and finishing with the archiving of documents.

Payment by clients will be made possible through the payment terminal installed in the premise of CISC, which will be connected to the ERLS.

However, the Concept of CISC could serve as a model for replication in local public authorities adjusting it to local needs.

3. Visegrad experience in ICT solutions for local services (with a focus on experience in legal regulations field) and best practices relevant to be approached by Moldova

3.1. Czech Republic experience

One of the first legal texts for large-scale state information systems was the Act No. 365/2000 Coll., On information systems of public administration¹⁰. It was designed to create appropriate legal environment for the implementation of the State Information Policy¹¹ and of the Concept on building public administration information systems¹².

The information systems of public administration functioning before the approval of the nominated act were not able to exchange information between the systems. Many data from citizens and legal entities were required repeatedly, the state authority for this area (the Office for the State Information System) did not have a clearly defined scope and competence.

The Act created legislative conditions for the effective use of information from various information systems of public administration ensuring gradual improvement of the existing situation.

An important step was to determine the most needed basic definitions in this area, particularly the concepts of information activities, such as: information system, manager and operator of public administration information system, the standard of public information systems, data element, composite data element, qualifier, table of keys, reference shared and secure interfaces of public information systems, remote access to the information system, portal of public administration, public and operational information system, etc..

¹⁰ http://www.portal-vz.cz/getmedia/c5466450-a309-4a22-8e0e-aeecdc9adf74/365_2000_zakon_o_ISVS

¹¹ Czech Republic Government Resolution dated 31 May 1999 no. 525 on the draft state information policy

¹² Czech Republic Government Resolution dated October 11, 1999 no. 1059

The scope of the Law defined the set of public information systems, which were used for public administration and were managed by public authorities, i.e. ministries, other administrative agencies, local authorities and other state authorities (with obvious exceptions in information systems operated by the military, police, intelligence services, etc.).

The existing Office for the State Information System was abolished and the new Office for Public Information Systems (OPSI) was established as the central administrative authority for the creation and development of information systems in public administration. The most important OPSI tasks were considered activities oriented to make more efficient information exchange between public administrations authorities and the public, especially re-use of already gathered information. Its competences were routed on the one hand into the technical and methodological assistance to entities pursued in information systems, on the other hand to solutions for over departmental common matters, namely: exchange of information through communication media. The OPSI essential business tool for public administration authorities were standards on public administration information systems, which had on the one hand the form of technical regulations e.g. to ensure the exchange of data and on the other hand in the form of organizational and methodological materials. However, OPSI was also equipped with sanctioning powers, relating to monitoring compliance with this law.

The responsibility for the creation and operation of information systems is under the competency of individual public authorities, in respecting government-approved documents in the field of public administration information systems. It is their obligation to comply with the general requirements common to all authorities of public administrations. Among other things, in this context great emphasis was put on the principle of openness, i.e. allow the disclosure of information about the structure of the information systems, so as to ensure general awareness about which data are stored by various competent public authorities.

To verify if the appropriate reference interface, product, service or information system meet the standards, quality of products and services and the degree of security of information systems, an attestation system was selected. The certification centres were specifically authorized by OPSI to issue relevant comparative type protocols.

The potential complexity of the application of the Law was clear already at its adoption; the timeframe of the Law implementation was up to 15 months. Information systems of public authorities had to be rebuilt in accordance with this Law or their activity had to be stopped.

Further steps were followed in accordance with the timetable set out in the concept of building information systems in public administration. A set of specific preparatory projects from different areas are of great importance. They were released in December 2001 and processed according to the specifications by the commercial sector:

- Services Directory (conceptual design) [Compaq]
- Central user support (conceptual design) [KPMG Consulting]
- Public Key Infrastructure (conceptual design) [IBM]
- Communication infrastructure and network management (conceptual design for managing the Communication Infrastructure) [ANECT's]
- Coordination of basic registers (conceptual design sub-project) [KPMG Consulting]
- Meta-information system (conceptual design) [Aquasoft s.r.o.]
- Access Portal (conceptual design) [IBM]
- Reference interface (conceptual design) [Deloitte & Touche].

In the legislative area, one of the main documents was the Act on public administration registers, the outline of the Czech government approved on December 3, 2001¹³.

At that time the rules of public administration registers were fragmented into many laws, that apply only to keeping each single registry. In addition, most of the above mentioned legislation did not explicitly establish registers in electronic form ; almost none of the registers in electronic form were considered legally binding; existing legislation did not forbid to enter false data to postpone the legal effect. Ambiguity was limited by law, that established the rights and obligations of public authorities regarding the sharing, communication and provision of the necessary data.

The aim of the Law was to establish uniform rules for the management and exploitation of public administration registers in electronic form, as a very broad and specific category of databases that are part of public administration information systems. The defined scope of the proposed law was narrow – it referred to three basic registers of public administration (basic register of inhabitants, basic register of economic entities, the basic register of territorial identification and real estate). However, the defined scope could be extended to other registers established by a special law and kept by public authorities, therefore it allowed for a gradual transformation of registers of public administration, depending on their technological and other readiness.

The proposal has included an additional set of necessary basic definitions in this field, particularly such concepts as the register of public administration, primary and reference data element, identifier, administrator and operator of the registry, the primary information resource site, the originator of the information, standard service, transmission, receipt, delivery and retrieval of data. With regard to the contents of registers, the act has assumed that their purpose, the subject of record keeping and a list of data, always set by special laws, which also determine, which data are expressed by identifiers, primary data elements and reference data elements. The aim was to eliminate multiple detection and recording of those data. The condition of trustworthiness with reference to data elements is necessary so that their contents could be transmitted to other registries and to prevent the spreading of incorrect or invalid information.

To support the performance of competencies of individual public administration authorities (within their statutory duties), these authorities can collect personal data from basic registers free of charge. Personal data from other registers may be retrieved by these authorities only to the extent determined by special laws.

Typical rights and duties of administrators, operators and others persons were also established. These included keeping logs of every activity carried out with registers and their regular evaluation, the possibility to view the data contents of the register at any date and time, responsibility for the factual correctness of the data elements etc.

OPSI for Public Information Systems record kept the list of registers, issued for each register datasheet, announced the standard of public information systems, which determined the content of the data sheet register, kept information system about data elements and data

¹³ The general principle of the law on public administration registers. Prague: ISI, 2001

sources, managed the service enabling data retrieval from the registers within the public administration portal and had sanctioning powers in relation to law implementation.

The proposed law has solved the issues of registers of public administration in general. Its implementation has started primary basic registers (BR):

- BR of Inhabitants – holds the data of inhabitants,
- BR of Persons – holds the data of companies and governmental agencies,
- BR of Territorial identification, addresses and real estates – holds the data of buildings.

The relationship with the business sector was an important part of creating basic registers..

Information systems operated by public administration by their nature belong to the sphere of public law and as such must be governed by the provisions of actual legislation.. On the other hand, information systems operated by the business sector are not always compliant to general legal standards. General rights and obligations are actually implemented secondarily, generally in relation to the operator (e.g. if the commercial entity is authorized to perform some functions of public administration), or to the content (e.g. classified information¹⁴, personal data¹⁵ and the accounting records¹⁶).

The interest of the business sector, however, is to be able to use data from public administration registers for a wide range of their needs from the basic records of persons (e.g. common HR) to owning a business with such information.

The registers are in principle publicly accessible, i.e. every person may inspect and take copies or extracts. This principle, however, for various reasons can not always be valid and therefore must be restricted by law, mainly in relation to personal data protection.

Given that the definition of data registers (especially basic) is widely used and all are interested in their update, data are to be provided freely to the public. A similar issue is citizens having access to data about themselves. The principle of free access to own data is based on the reciprocity of the relationship between public administration and the subject.

Conclusion

The goal of all of the effort was to create conditions for the optimal use of data sources, to use in certain information systems the information already acquired in other information systems, effectively restrict the content and scope of information systems still in operation and thus reduce government costs in this area. A very important social feature of the use of information services of registers of public administration in this context should be more comfort for the citizen when dealing with authorities, reducing unnecessary bureaucracy and greater transparency for the private sector as well.

I think, that problems mentioned above concern to the current conditions in the field of building information system in public administration in Moldova.

¹⁴ Act no. 148/1998 Coll., On protection of classified information and amending certain laws

¹⁵ Act no. 101/2000 Coll., On protection of personal data and amending certain laws, as amended.

¹⁶ Act no. 563/1991 Coll., On Accounting, as amended.

3.2. Slovakia experience

The experience of Slovak Republic (SR) in the area of e-Government building, with focus on building the legal environment proves that it is important to harmonize the legal framework and development of informatics in the country, including changes in processes and agendas of public administration, being in line with competences division both in central government and between central and local governments. It is important to take into account not only the competences in the area of informatics, but also the competences in the agendas of public administration. regarding the development of legal framework from ICT services point of view, it is important to follow plans for building IT architecture and clearly announce what will be developed for central level and local level, what is the timeframe and what is expected as contribution of local government. The term **public administration** refers to state government on central and regional level, as well as regional and local self-government.

The legal framework in the area of informatics in Slovakia was created on the basis of some historical principles. In the accession period, before joining the EU it was affected by EU legal framework and obligation to reach EU level,;after joining the EU it is an integral part of Slovak legal framework. ***From this experience and point of view it is also advisable for Moldova to take now into account EU legal framework for informatics and to watch further EU plans and development.***

EU legislation

EU legislation is a parent to national legislation for the same regulated areas. Legal decrees have a various levels of legal power – some of them coming into force just after adoption (regulations), some of them are subject of transposition and changes of national legislation (directives). Some of them are specifically binding for concrete addressee (decisions). Besides mentioned cases, there are also others, which usually have the level of recommendations (not binding). But it is important to take also these regulations into account, because many times they only announce in advance future regulations of unique reforms. ***Taking them into account now can save money in the future.***

Slovak legislation

National level of legal decrees consists mainly from various laws, orders, acts, arrangements, but also regulations and decisions (these mostly with specific power).

The main advisory and consultancy body for legislation in area of information society is ***Commission for legislation in area of information society***, which is established by the Ministry of Finance of SR, which is the competent body for coordination of informatics matters in Slovakia. Members of the Commission are mainly legislative experts acting as members of public administration bodies or as academic sector members.

Analysis of legislative framework in SR in line with information society

Considering the cardinal impact of informatics (referring to feeding eServices and digitization of various processes) on the whole legislative framework in the country, it is important to consistently analyse each single legal decree (starting from laws and ending with generally binding regulations of territorial self-governments), to reach their harmonization and to eliminate potential barriers.

This task is very complicated, because of a huge number of decrees, as well as living process of its changes.

Approval process in Slovakia

A specific legislative area is the so called approval (sometimes referred to as legislative) process. The majority of materials proposed by state administration bodies on the national level are submitted to Government or to relevant Government councils (eventually to both). Regardless if the material is of legislative (as laws etc.) or non-legislative (as strategies etc.) character, it needs to have closure of influences on various areas, which include economy, employment, environment, but also informatics. The application of this closure meant an important shift, because the proponent of a legal decree is obliged to think on these influences and describe them in detail. The target is that new legal decrees do not have a negative influence on information society, but support its development. For the process of influences description there is a *Unique methodology, which deals in details with all types of influences and defines approaches of proponents*.

Legislative stream

Computerisation of the whole approval process was one of the significant steps to improvement of transparency and an instrument, which allowed reading submitted proposals of legal decrees independently of readers location. It is obligatory for the whole public sector from 01.06.2008 to publish proposals of legal documents including their attachments on the Portal of legal documents and to collect comments this way. One part of portal is a Unique information system for observation of legislative process, including various statistical and graphical functions, serving to proposer and government as tools for better assessment of comments and influences to target groups. Also *comments to published proposals are collected electronically using this portal*. It is publicly available and no confirmation in paper form is requested .

EU Legislation relevant for Information Society area

The list of EU legal documents with direct influence on information society development (ordered according to the date of entering into force) is provided in the **Annex No. 2** to this Study.

Besides this group of legal decrees, there is a number of additional cross-sectional legal decrees, which refer to informatics only partially. Some of them are also listed in the attachment.

It is important to realize that the list in Annex 2 can not be actual or absolute, due to various ongoing processes in the approval life cycle (proposal, comments, assessment of comments, writing of new version, submission to the approval body/bodies, etc.). The list offers the framework view of the main documents and more actual information is available on EU portal Eur-lex (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu>).

Legislation of SR relevant for Information Society area

The responsible body for state informatics is the Ministry of Finance of SR, but additional Central bodies of state administration also have competences in this respect. Legal decrees were divided depending on the responsibilities of the main body and additional bodies.

Responsible body: MF SR

Law 275/2006 about information systems of public administration (in effect from 1.6.2006)

In amendments 678/2006 (in effect from 1.2.2007), 553/2008 (from 1.2.2009), 570/2009 (from 1.2.2010), 289/2012 (from 1.11.2012), 202/2013 1.9.2013)

Act 55/2014 about standards for information systems of public administration (in effect from 15.3.2014)

In amendments 276/2014 (in effect from 15.10.2014), 137/2015 (in effect from 1.7.2015)

Previous versions:

Act 478/2010 about the basic classifier of public administration segments and about agendas of public administration (in effect from 1.1.2011)

Law 305/2013 about electronic version of operation of public bodies power and about changes of some laws (law about e-Government) (in effect from 1.11.2013)

Order 25/2014 about integral service points and conditions for its establishments, registrations, labelling, operation and about rates tariff (in effect from 15.2.2014)

In amendment 3/2015 (in effect from 15.2.2015)

Act of Ministry of Finance MF/009269/2014-173 about unique format of electronic messages created and sent through entry places (in effect from 15.4.2014)

Intent of law about information security - important legal regulations under development by Ministry of Finance

Other responsible bodies (Central bodies of Public Administration)

Law 215/2002 about eSignature (in effect from 1.5.2002)

In amendments 679/2004 (1.1.2006), 25/2006 (1.2.2006), 275/2006 (1.6.2006), 214/2008 (1.1.2009)

Order of the National Security Office 131/2009 about certificates and qualified certificates (in effect from 26.3.2009)

In amendment 60/2014 (efficiency from 15.3.2014)

Orders of National Security Office 133/2009, 134/2009, 135/2009, 136/2009 about various aspects of eSignature usage and process of certification and verification in its amendments in 2014 (all are in effect)

Law 351/2011 on e-Communications

Law 22/2004 on e-Commerce (in effect from 1.2.2004)

In amendment 160/2005 (in effect from 1.5.2005)

Law 220/2007 about digital transmission (in effect from 31.5.2007)

Law 45/2011 about critical infrastructure (in effect from 1.3.2011)

Act of Ministry of Interior 525/2011 about standards for electronic information systems for administration of registry (in effect from 1.2.2012)

Law 153/2013 about national health information system (in effect from 1.7.2013)

Actual and additional information is available on webpages of issuers www.nbusr.sk, www.telecom.gov.sk, www.economy.gov.sk, www.employment.gov.sk

Other relevant decrees for Information Society:

Law 215/1995 about geodesy and cartography (in effect from 1.1.2006) – part about automated IS of geodesy, cartography and cadastre

Law 253/2000 about free access to information (Aarhus agreement) (in effect from 1.1.2001)

In amendments 546/2010 (1.1.2011), 382/2011 (1.1.2012)

Law 540/2001 about state statistics (in effect from 1.1.2002)

Law 530/2003 about business register (in effect from 1.2.2004)

Law 618/2003 about copyright and about rights connected with copyright (in effect from 1.1.2004) – the part about copyrights in digital environment

Law 215/2004 about restricted facts (in effect from 1.5.2004) – the part about restricted facts in digital version

Law 300/2005 about Criminal codex (in effect from 1.1.2006) – the part relating to faults and criminal acts by electronic facilities and in electronic environment

Law 3/2010 about national infrastructure for spatial information (in effect from 1.2.2010) – requirements for GIS

Law 122/2013 about protection of personal data and about the change and amendment of some laws (in effect from 1.7.2013) – protection of personal data, including in electronic environment.

Actual versions of laws are on the Unique automated portal of legal information (<http://jaspi.justice.gov.sk>), which is operated by the Ministry of Justice. This portal is also very important for e-Government. All legal documents, also of a lower statute, are published in the electronic collection of legal decrees <http://www.zbierka.sk/>

3.3 Poland experience

Development of ICT solutions for local services is based upon several general regulations regarding:

- IT systems development,
- Interoperability,
- Electronic signature and electronic documents,
- Personal data protection,
- Provision of public information,
- General Informatisation plan (guidelines more than requirements).

Apart from those regulations there are many sub-regulations in different bills (i.e. cadastral, social security, health, tax, administration, civil law) that have to be taken into an account in particular situations.

The regulations in Poland do not form a comprehensive and very strict law. This leads to massive lack of interoperability and continuity on one hand. On the other hand it enables to test different approaches to the problems.

Each authority develops its own set of services – very often it is not clear if some authority provides certain service – and what certain service really means.

The public procurement law is very important from the point of view of IT development. Generally speaking, this law was not meant for very specific technology issues – for instance, it is quite difficult to include a presentation as a criterion of choice. The other drawback is that one cannot easily calculate risk / price ratio.

The public procurement is a subject of very annoying legal feuds. There are negative consequences of legal decisions, the superiority of rhetoric over merit and powerlessness of courts necessary to rule on issues requiring formidable IT competence.

The settled doctrine and the surprising decision of the National Appeal Chamber (KIO) repeatedly cast a shadow over the way orders are reinforcing the bad practices of IT buyers and suppliers, who are often powerless in the face of limited perception faced with the challenge of arbitrators to rule on matters which require knowledge of complex technological nuances.

It is important to stress that a good law has to be placed in good environment – qualified and motivated staff.

The other problem is the budgetary system. Very often money are budgeted per one year. This leads to a situation when a project cannot be started and finished properly because the period is too short.

4. Lessons learnt: ICT solutions for local services (with a focus on experience in legal regulations field)

4.1. Czech Republic experience

Successful implementation of ICT solution for local services at central and local (region, district) levels is not possible without:

1. Creation of the legislative and normative environment for all ISPA, including implementation regulations.
2. Credible information resources, which are needed for providing trusted electronic transactions and services.
3. Creation of a methodology for every service, as a base for software development.
4. Defining the role and relationship of commercial structures in ICT solutions for local services.
5. Defining the role and relationship of commercial structures in providing information for ISPA.

In all points mentioned above, an irreplaceable role is played by well-defined laws, orders, regulations, implementation of regulations and of technical standards.

If these basic conditions are not respected and implemented, there are big loses of resources (money, time, labour).

4.2. Slovakia experience

As underlined in the previous chapter, it is necessary to take into account EU legislation in information society sector and responsibly build the national segment, thinking on its implementation at all levels, national, regional and local. The basic principles must be set equally for the whole country. The specific differences can be adopted on the local level, but

a research should be carried out when creating such documents, to examine the similar situations in other local governments. If that is the case, the law content should be harmonized across the whole local level.

4.3 Poland experience

It is very important to make sure that legal acts enable / require proper approach to IT projects:

- It is essential to have a separate payment regulations to IT people – very often young people gather knowledge and experience and then free the position.
- It is quite important to force LPA to use electronic mailboxes (like ePUAP in Poland or the Czechboxes).
- It is necessary to implement good practices in IT development and maintenance standards, like:
 - a. Prince2 / PMBOK / IPMA (project management),
 - b. ITIL v3 / ISO 20000 (services maintenance),
 - c. COBIT / ISO 27001 / OWASP (security)
- It is usually very difficult to develop local-central services cooperation. It is good to develop mid-size platforms, that combine e-services and data from certain regions (for instance northern, central and southern regions – „Regiunea de dezvoltare”).
- Physical aspect of IT is very important, therefore it is good to develop regional data centres – regulations must require LPA to use them.
- The register of e-services definitions must be maintained centrally.
- Public procurement law has to be revised in order to enable IT procurement to go along properly.
- It is important to provide some kind of standardisation of IT systems, which on one side enables to open the IT market do different players, and on the other increases the efficiency.
- Very often LPA lacks the vision of the role of the state and administration informatization, because they don't take into account the opportunities related to new technologies and LPA's lack of awareness on the importance of effectiveness in public administration management,
- Common problems are ill-defined performance objectives and institutional processes, as well as the attachment to paper-based administrative processes.
- Very often LPAs lack the assessment of investments for compliance with the objectives of the results.

4.4. Moldova experience

Although the legal and regulatory environment of the Republic of Moldova for ICT based services is in the process of continuous development and approximation to that of the European Union, the level of ICT-based local services is insufficient.

The speed of e-Transformation agenda implementation is not yet at the necessary level. Moreover, a substantial gap exists between the level of services offered at the central level and those offered at the local level.

The 2 important documents: Public Administration Reform Program and The National Action Plan for the implementation of the RM-EU Association Agreement 2014-2016, as well as e-Transformation Agenda are an essential foundation (if implemented) for the creation of legal/regulatory environment for the development of ICT based services.

The Laws: On electronic signature and electronic document, On reuse of information, On Registers, On State Information Resources, On Electronic Communications and other relevant laws in place are forming the legal basis for ICT based services in Moldova. However the level of implementation and of respecting rule of law is yet insufficient.

The basic registers: Population Register, Legal Entities Register, Addresses Register (not fully functional) are in place and form a basis for functioning of other public authorities information systems.

The platforms created within the e-Transformation agenda implementation (MCloud, MSign, MPay, MPass, SIGEDIA and others) and relevant Government Decisions on their implementation, form a good foundation for implementation of e-services.

The lack of interoperability between Public Authorities Information systems creates issues in exchange of data between public authorities.

There is a lack of methodological norms, semantic catalogues and standards in building Information systems for local authorities of Moldova.

Although e-Transformation units were created in CPA, there is a lack of high level professionals in these units, because of the insufficient level of salaries.

The solution for local ICT-based services is being implemented in Moldova: Citizen Information and Service Centre (CISC) pioneered by USAID Local Government Support in Moldova¹⁷. Integrated information system of the mayor's office will be based on the Electronic Registry of Local Services (ERLS) and the System for Issuing Permissive Documents (SIPD). The IRLS and SIPD will operate on the M-Cloud platform provided by the [e-Government Centre](#).

5. Findings of the scientific seminar: ICT solutions for local services (legal regulations)

The discussions within the seminar confirmed the findings of other projects research, surveys on ICT based local public services.

The existing legal and regulatory framework provides that local authorities must offer different types of public services.

¹⁷ <http://www.chemonics.com/OurWork/OurProjects/Pages/Moldva-Local-Government-Support-Project-.aspx>

Survey data ¹⁸ shows that of the 22 locally supplied services, such as issuance of various documents to citizens, most in demand are: certificate about family - 20.7%; payment of taxes - 14.9%; certificate on place of residence - 13.0%; certificate about possession (loss) of share of agricultural land - 10.6%; extract from the land register - 6.1%; certificate on lack of debts to the national public budget and certificate of ownership - by 5.9%.

The other services are required in a much smaller proportion, such as certificate on lack of workbook certificate - 0,7% or authorization of placing advertising devices - 0.8%.

The level of access of institutions and public authorities web pages of for information or to obtain public services is under 25%. The most requested information concerns: medical services- 23.3%, culture - 12.3%, legislation amendments- 11.9%, governmental institutions - 11.0%.

This is explained by market underdevelopment of public services on-line (including the local absence of some of them), the perception that Internet users choose to pursue leisure and recreation interests, information functions at the expense of performance or electronics.

As the Survey found out, the lack of databases and software for electronic data processing results in increased duration of service provision. Currently, the information about the population in most municipalities is collected manually, in registers. Thus, over several years, the mayoralties have compiled records in 9-12 registers and in order to search data about the citizen, requesting a document, time is needed to check the data from archives, books and find the necessary information. For the officials who have been working for several years in the City Hall it is much easier to find the data / information required for issuing certificates and therefore the duration is shorter.

Some municipalities have purchased cadastral programs or the "secretary plus" specialists, that facilitate the work of the LPA. Their purchases were made at the initiative of the City Hall. Municipalities that do not have such data processing programs, resort to traditional methods of work (obviously in paper records). Refusal to purchase and install electronic data processing programs is motivated by the high cost and the lack of knowledge in managing these programs.

The existing situation is also conditioned by the lack of information systems and lack of inter-networking between information systems and institutions. The lack of online and / or offline communication between the officials and institutions, to check data and information of legal or natural persons forces the beneficiary to fulfil the role of "courier" between different institutions or offices by themselves to obtain the necessary documentation. This fact justifies the urgent need to reform public services, including basic digitization and reengineering services to eliminate uncomfortable and inefficient processes.

Lack of computer software applications is one of the main difficulties related to the quick provision of local public services. Currently, in most municipalities the basic information is stored in paper records. Digitizing records and automating their management would streamline the work of public servants. However, only the digitization will not solve the problem permanently. The need for interrelated records services between institutions is also important. Interoperability of services based on PA government-to-government platform would fully optimize any flow of public services, providing opportunities for officials to

¹⁸ Study: Servicii publice administrative prestate la nivel local: diagnostic și oportunități de e-Transformare. Elaborat cu suportul PNUD/PCDL de către: *Centrul de Investigații Sociologice și Marketing „CBS-AXA” Institutul de Dezvoltare Urbană, 2014.*

extract, verify, validate, provide data registries and databases systems quickly and at minimal costs.

To implement on-line service delivery at the local level, several participants mentioned the necessity to focus on needs. As a priority, they relate to: (i) providing equipment and computers, (ii) developing procurement databases and electronic data processing programs, (iii) data processing of archive records accumulated in City Halls.

In addition to supplying equipment and technical facilities needed at the local level, there is an urgent need to reduce the number of certificates and documents required for issuing different acts.

Specialists within LPA reform implementation highlighted the need to digitize public services throughout the territory of the country, by creating *a single common system of service provision*. But first it is necessary to ensure service functionality, both technically and in terms of human resources. However, it may be emphasized and stated that local authorities are to promote and actively explore new opportunities for public services in electronic mode, including the launch of local pilot services, such as requesting and obtaining notification of payment of taxes, the certificate on place of residence, certificate about family, the extract from the Land Registry.

LPAs are also faced with a number of problems related particularly to the current organization, and especially to the insufficiency of resources for the implementation of ICT solutions, such as¹⁹:

- the lack of registries in hard copy of the services provided, and the lack of record keeping of services, respectively;
- insufficient resources (for e.g. cars, funds for covering the telephone costs, in some cases, the computers used are old and need to be replaced);
- the risk of discontinuing some services which are provided only by one person, whose absence makes it impossible to further provide them;
- low storage security of documents/information (for example, there is no fire alarm system for the hard copy archives in the LPA offices);
- insufficient licensed programs, lack of automated programs for documents handling;
- limited communication at the level of electronic data exchange between LPAs, DSs, and other local actors, the lack of corporative e-mail addresses.

The participants to the Seminar mainly confirmed the above-mentioned issues and underlined a range of issues in implementation of e-services on local level, such as:

- lack of political will
- lack of information campaigns for the citizen and of training for civil servants in rural areas;
- documents duplication;
- lack of pilot projects from the central level to raion - and from raion to cities/villages which could be undertaken for multiplication in other localities;
- resistance to change;

¹⁹ Concept of Citizen Information and Service Center

<http://www.descentralizare.gov.md/lib.php?l=en&idc=446&t=/DRAFTS-IN-DISCUSSION/Concept-of-Citizen-Information-and-Service-Center>

- lack of experts group who would consult and support local authorities in e-services implementation;
- lack of a partnership network (central government, local, civil society, business etc.)
- local authorities are the main/biggest data providers, but at the same time they do not have access to these data
- necessity of a stocktaking of all public authorities possessions (in terms of ICT, information systems etc.)
- Moldova has good strategies but there is a lack of finance for a better implementation of all plans, documents.

Given the issues identified within the Seminar discussions and taking into consideration the finding of Study²⁰ and other above-mentioned documents, the following recommendations for promoting and implementing local public services on-line are to be taken into consideration:

- Provide public information campaigns on the benefits of on-line local public services.
- Editing and distributing tutorials on how to access and obtain e-services.
- Diversify the channels of public information on the processes taking place in local authorities, including by electronic means.
- Providing support and technical assistance, advisory to supply municipalities with equipment and modern computers.
- Promote the concept of outsourcing (outsourcing of services) and attracting investments for modernization of the LPA.
- Providing technical and specialized assistance in computer equipment maintenance for local governments.
- Provide assistance and logistical and technical support for the development of databases and electronic data processing programs.
- Provide technical and logistical assistance required to process data records from the archives accumulated in municipalities.
- Strengthen knowledge, skills of local civil servants on the use of information technology and data security and information assurance, possibly within centers of excellence in e-governance and e-public services.
- Implementation of pilot projects in local authority for testing mechanisms in providing on-line services.
- Promoting the creation of attractive conditions within municipalities for attracting and hiring young specialists.
- Operation of changes in the legal framework that would allow reduction of the number of certificates issued for local public services.

²⁰ Study: Servicii publice administrative prestate la nivel local: diagnostic și oportunități de e-Transformare. Elaborat cu suportul PNUD/PCDL de către: *Centrul de Investigații Sociologice și Marketing „CBS-AXA” Institutul de Dezvoltare Urbană, 2014.*

- Systemic approach, coordinated nationally, based on the principles of subsidiarity of the problems of implementation of e-services in local government.
- Conducting scientific research, studies on the premises and societal impact of electronic public services, particularly in local government, that are the main providers of services; for prioritization and objectives, identifying the best solutions and joint efforts of all social actors in the implementation of e-Government.
- Develop a suitable methodological framework to the new realities on the implementation and provision of e-services in local governments.
- Encouraging the private sector and civil society to participate in developing and implementing advanced solutions for telecommunications, based on the latest achievements in information technology and communications, public management, in other relevant areas: e-commerce, e-medicine, e-education etc.
- Implementation, at LPA of pilot projects in public management solutions locally and dissemination of best practices at the national level.
- Implementation of necessary technical standards as important component for e-services
- Planning money for ICT in local budget .
- The bottom-up approach in implementation of local services - local servants should manifest initiative and wish.

6. Recommendations on public policies, regulations/ amendments for the relevant public authorities from Moldova

6.1. Czech Republic recommendations

The central authorities should issue laws, with the content corresponding to the following laws:

- **The first group:**

Act No. 365/2000 Col. „On information systems of public administration”and subsequent i.e.:

Act No. 111/2009 Col. „On the Basic Registries”

Regulation No. 469/2006 Col. „On Information system about data elements”

Regulation No. 528/2006 Col. „On Information system about Information systems of Public Administration”

Regulation „On attestation of the information systems of public administration”

- **The second group:**

Act No. 499/2004 Col. „On archival business and office-work” and subsequent, i.e.:

Regulation No. 212/2012 „On office-work“

Act No. 227/2000 Col. „On electronics signature“

Act No.500/2004 Col. „Administrative rules”

MoReq 2 — Model requirements for the management of electronic documents.

- **The third group:**

Act No. 300/2008 Col. „On electronic certificates, personal numbers and the authorised converting of documents”

For all laws it is necessary to issue the implementing regulations.

In parallel with this work, it is necessary to develop and codify a terminology for public administration. („Nu există o terminologie specială pentru administrația publică, ...”, pag. 64, Ghidul funcționarului public. Ediția a opta actualizată. Chișinău, Inst. de Filologie al AȘM, 2012).

But first, regardless of the current situation, it is necessary to prepare a draft national environment for ISPA i.e. code pages, character names and symbols, rules for transliteration and transcription rules for sorting characters, etc. *Because this is a complex process, mentioned by many participants, it should be discussed in detail.*

6.2. Slovakia recommendations

Moldova has signed the association agreement with the EU and is on the route to join the EU. Between the EU countries there is an agreement about common assets and rules, where e-Government and digital market are one of the bearing attributes, the recommendation is, that Moldova takes into account now the legal framework of the EU in the area of informatics and information society. It is also necessary to observe and understand further developments in this area at the EU level. Based on this developments, it is advisable to create and modify the national legislation as well.

Besides the adopted legal decrees, the EU is also publishing recommendations as in early advices about the direction of further unique layout. It is necessary if possible, to take them into account as well, because it can save resources in the future.

In terms of legal decrees for the area of informatics on local level, it is advisable have a coordinated approach and adopt modifications on the local level in the same manner in the whole country. Such practice will bring benefits for citizens and entrepreneurs. It will also bring advantages for the public sector, at least for the exchange of data and for statistical comparisons.

For the approval process of legal decrees on the national level it is advisable to establish (if it hasn't been done yet) an obligation for proponents to describe in detail the influences of a proposed legal decree on information society, and reduce negative influences as much as possible. The similar mechanism is advisable to be implemented on the local level too.

An additional recommendation is to establish a Portal of legal decrees for the legislation approval process, setting the obligation to submit proposals only through this portal. This portal should be publicly available, with requirement to submit comments by authorities, as well as general public.

6.3 Poland recommendations

Recommendations on public policies, regulation / amendments are the following:

1. It is quite useful to buy / provide key technology at central / regional level. This leads to massive cost reductions. For instance, in Poland it is the governmental Electronic Document Management.
2. At the same time deployment of the common technology should be put on the market to enable smaller local companies to benefit.
3. It is important to have a separate way to remunerate IT staff.
4. It is good to include IT procurement specifics in Public Procurement Laws:
 - a. Ability to take the aspects like risk, service and experience into account,
 - b. Ability to include expertise in the tenders.
5. It is very important to standardize procedures used in local authorities and build e-services upon already standardized procedures. The ideal is to use BPMN notation.
6. It is very important to have general plan of IT development, including guidelines and recommendations. However some kind of local autonomy must be provided to adjust general guidelines to local situation.
7. Every bill has to have moneys attached to it – it should be clear what cost each bill generates and where those money come from.
8. It is necessary to include the punishment clauses in each bill – formulating requirements with co-consequences leads to misconduct.
9. Budgetary system has to take into account the fact that IT projects last longer than one year.

7. Conclusions on recommendations on public policies, regulations/ amendments for the relevant public authorities from Moldova

1. To succeed in implementation of ICT based services at the local level the country-wide approach is necessary to be applied.
2. The best practices from V4 countries provided in the present paper have to be additionally analysed through already planned actions in the existing documents in the field of Information Society development in the Republic of Moldova.
3. The National Action Plan for the implementation of the RM-EU Association Agreement 2014-2016²¹, approved by Government Decision on 25 June 2014 is one of the most important documents in approximation of legal framework on Information Society and ICT based services to those of the EU.
4. The second relevant document is the Public Services Reform Program approved by the Government and recently updated²² containing provisions at the extent that they concern ICT based local public services, is to be followed.

²¹ Approved by Government Decision on 25 June 2014

²² Government Decision nr.198 of 23.04.2015

5. The third document to be followed is the Briefing Book from Development Partners (January, 2015)²³
6. The most recent document is the Government of Moldova Activity Program 2015-2018 (see the relevant Excerpt in the Annex 5)
7. The documents to be developed recommended by V4 experts are partially covered by the Program and by the National Action Plan.
8. It is suggested to have a coordinated approach for legal decrees in the area of informatics on local level in the whole country, as much as possible.
9. The basic principles must be set equally for the whole country. The specific differences can be adopted on the local level but a research should be carried out when creating such documents, to examine the similar situations in other local governments. If that is the case, the law content should be harmonized across the whole local level. The <http://www.actelocale.md/> platform shall be used for ensuring the proposed approach and for transparency of local authorities.
10. . Such practice will bring benefits for citizens and entrepreneurs. It will also bring advantages for the public sector, at least for the exchange of data and for statistical comparisons.
11. For the approval process of legal decrees on national level is advisable to use the participation approach (already established through the portal www.particip.gov.md).
12. Access to basic registers: Population Register, Register of Legal Entities, Addresses Register has to be ensured for all public authorities according to legal provisions.
13. Balanced approach between respecting protection of personal data and access to necessary data for effective and efficient functionality of ICT based services by public authorities.
14. It is quite useful to buy / provide key technology at central / regional level. This leads to massive cost reductions.²⁴
15. The “Paperless Government” initiative in Moldova was planned to be implemented, so as from the beginning of 2014 the offices of hundreds of public officials working in ministries, agencies and departments had to be paper free. However, in spite of the fact that SIGEDIA Documents Management System was piloted in 9 ministries, only the Ministry of Education declared paperless document management inside the institution implemented as from April, 2015.
16. It is necessary to analyse and understand the implementation problem of SIGEDIA and find alternatives in Document Management System Implementation. This is an issue that can be discussed on the DISCUS platform.
17. Deployment of the common technology should be put on the market to enable smaller local companies to benefit.
18. It is important to have a separate way to remunerate IT staff.
19. It is good to include IT procurement specifics in Public Procurement Laws:

²³ <http://www.worldbank.org/en/country/moldova/publication/briefing-book>

²⁴ For instance in Poland’s governmental Electronic Document Management.

- a. Ability to take the aspects like risk, service and experience into account,
 - b. Ability to include expertise in the tenders.
20. It is very important to standardize procedures used in local authorities and build e-services upon already standardized procedures. The ideal is to use BPMN notation.
 21. It is very important to have general plan of IT development, including guidelines and recommendations. However some kind of local autonomy must be provided to adjust general guidelines to local situation.
 22. Every bill has to have moneys attached to it – it should be clear what cost each bill generates and where are those money come from.
 23. It is necessary to include the punishment clauses in each bill – formulating requirements with consequences leads to misconduct.
 24. Budgetary system has to take into account the fact that the IT projects last longer than one year.
 25. Provide public information campaigns on the benefits of on-line local public services.
 26. Editing and distributing tutorials on how to access and obtain e-services.
 27. Diversify the channels of public information on the processes taking place in local authorities, including by electronic means.
 28. Providing support and technical assistance, advisory to supply municipalities with equipment and modern computers.
 29. Promote the concept of outsourcing (outsourcing of services) and attracting investments for modernization of the LPA.
 30. Providing technical and specialized assistance in computer equipment maintenance for local governments.
 31. Provide assistance and logistical and technical support for the development of databases and electronic data processing programs.
 32. Provide technical and logistical assistance required to process data records from the archives accumulated in municipalities.
 33. Strengthen knowledge, skills of local civil servants on the use of information technology and data security and information assurance, possibly within centers of excellence in e-governance and e-public services.
 34. Implementation of pilot projects in local authority for testing mechanisms in providing on-line services.
 35. Promoting the creation of attractive conditions within municipalities for attracting and hiring young specialists.
 36. Operation of changes in the legal framework that would allow the reduction of the number of certificates issued for local public services.
 37. Systemic approach, coordinated nationally, based on the principles of subsidiarity of the problems of implementation of e-services in local government.
 38. Conducting scientific research, studies on the premises and societal impact of electronic public services, particularly in local government, that are the main

providers of services; for prioritization and objectives, identifying the best solutions and joint efforts of all social actors in the implementation of e-Government.

39. Develop a suitable methodological framework to the new realities on the implementation and provision of e-services in local governments.
40. Encouraging the private sector and civil society to participate in developing and implementing advanced solutions for telecommunications, based on the latest achievements in information technology and communications, public management, in other relevant areas: e-commerce, e-medicine e-education etc.
41. Implementation in LPA of the pilot projects in public management solutions locally and dissemination of best practices at the national level.
42. Implementation of necessary technical standards, as important component for e-services
43. Planning money for ICT in local budgets.
44. The bottom-up approach in implementation of local services - to take into consideration the local servants initiatives and wishes.

Besides the listed actions, the following documents already included in action plans are to be developed, discussed, promoted and approved:

- law on public services
- law on archiving of electronic documents
- the methodology for the re-engineering of public services
- the framework methodology for setting tariffs for public services rendered against payment
- public policy proposal on centres for universal public services
- the methodology for drafting administrative regulations for public services
- the Government decision on government notification service (MNotify)
- the Government decision on government delivery service (MDelivery)
- the Government decision on the organization and functioning of the electronic document management information and records (SIGEDIA)
- the methodology for default digitization of public services
- amendments to the Regulation on single government portal content management of public services in connection with the development of the updated version (V2.0) of servicii.gov.md portal, and integration of electronic public services portal
- regulations and procedures for access and use of the interoperability platform
- Government Decision “On state Register of local authorities Regulations ”

Table 1. Identified issues, possible ICT based solutions for local services and recommendations on public polices for relevant public authorities											
Main issues identified within workshop (March 2015)	UNDP JILDP identified issues	USAID LGSP identified issues	Briefing book from Development Partners identified issues	Main issues identified within the Seminar nr.1 (May 2015)	Main issues identified in the Public Service Reform Program	Briefing book from Development Partners recommendations	Czech relevant solution/ recommendation	Polish relevant solution/ recommendation	Slovak relevant solution	USAID LGSP proposed solution	Consolidated recommendations on Public polices
Certificates issuing (family composition etc.)	Lack of digitalized registers	Services are provided in different locations (offices, floors), in the LPA premise, which fact makes it difficult for the citizens to immediately find the person(s) providing the given service(s); Insufficient information about the procedure for service provision, relevant	Business process reengineering has lagged behind, both at the centre and in local government, and is the most important public administration challenge ahead Bring e-Transformation to the level of local government: this will be improving government transactions: both Government-to-Government and Government-to-Citizen.	Lack of information campaigns for the citizen and of training for civil servants in rural area; - documents duplication; - lack of pilot projects from the central level to raion - and from raion to cities/villages which could be undertaken for multiplication in other localities; - resistance to the change; - lack of experts group who would consult and support local authorities in e-services implementation	Incomplete information posted on the public institutions websites Arbitrary inclusion of additional requirements beyond of normative acts Lack of uniform and transparent principles for establishing tariffs for paid services The absence of a clear definition of public services and public service diversity in legislation	Issue a Government Decree allowing government data to be used by the private sector, academia, and local government Approve the Law on Public Services and Government, in line with the EU Digital Agenda, 2020, eGovernment Agenda, Operational Data Strategy and Cloud Computing Strategy; Approve Policy Decisions and Regulations to enable the data exchange and interoperability through Government Platform MConnect, and to	System of the Shared Services in the Czech Republic EGON. EGON consist of Communications infrastructure including CMS (central interconnect) Basic registers: (People, Companies, Land and Houses, EU Rights and Duties) • Databoxes • Czech POINT • Governmental portal • List of OVM (Register of offices) • JIP/KAAS – unified identity space for public servants This system is intended to providing of elec	Development of e-Services needs to be done step by step. The goal of the first step should be: 1. Let people know that they may contact office via internet and encourage them to use. 2. Test the organisations capability in the small scale. Local authorities should consider developing the following types of Information Systems: 1. Basic Internet services, 2. Document Management System, 3. GIS systems, Citizen portal.	Develop e-Services: • based on your competencies • based on your original data • make links to original sources for other relevant data • without duplication of central Government work • based on life situation of client – but complex to cover the whole process • use interpretation on maps (GIS or Google maps)	Citizen Information and Service Centre (CISC): Integrated information system of the mayor's office will be based on the Electronic Registry of Local Services (ERLS) and the System for Issuing Permissive Documents (SIPD). The IRLS and SIPD will operate on the M-Cloud platform provided by the E-Governmen	A. Implementation of provisions of the Public services Reform program: Develop and promote a draft law on public services Development and promotion of the draft law on archiving electronic documents Drafting and approving the methodology of the re-engineering of public services Preparation and approval framework methodology for setting tariffs for public services rendered against payment Drafting and approving public policy proposal centres on universal
Archive services / lack of record keeping of services	Lack of digitalized registers										
Cadastral Excerpts (building permits, excerpts from property register, etc.)	Lack of interoperability										
Certificates on Tax debts	Lack of access to relevant information source										
Social Insurance											
Services are provided in different offices/no	Lack of information systems for LPA and interoperability										

<p>one stop-shop office</p>	<p>between decentralised services Lack of on-line/off-line communication between different public servants from different institutions</p>	<p>regulations, list of documents requested, terms of execution, etc.; Regardless of the fact that there are one-stop shops within LPAs, the applicants submit a set of required documents which is attached to the request by physically showing up at the mayor's office. The request for services in remote mode (via internet, telephone, fax) is not possible;</p>		<p>- lack of partnership network (central government, local, civil society, business etc.)</p>	<p>The absence of unified approved guidelines on analysis and services reengineering</p>	<p>enforce the “Only Once” Principle of Data submission by the population and businesses to government. Align Moldova Legal Framework with the EU Framework of Interoperability of Pan-European Public Service Delivery; Ensure personal data protection, as well as align relevant legislation with EU standards, and implement effectively; and Approve and enforce cyber security policy, regulations and implementation mechanisms to ensure secure digital communication, interactions, and transactions between people, businesses and government in Moldova and in the EU Single</p>	<p>tronics services on regional and local levels. Regional services: - Regional networks interconnect - Regional shared services centres - Public services digital map - Document management. Local services: - Statutory cities shared services centres - Cities shared services centres - Czech points front offices - Public services digital map - Document management</p>	<p>The first approach to public e-services: Identify stakeholders that could be interested in going digital. Enable possibility to send applications via e-mail without the need to get to the office personally. Implement procedures that trigger right action on the side of the authority upon the receipt of the application. The resulting service might be delivered via traditional mail. Implement PKI structure so that signed applications may be treated as written ones. Identify all the procedures in the office and describe them</p>	<p>Make coalition of local authorities: • by developing and sharing applications • (sharing of expenditures) • Think for structure of your e-Services • the client would be not lost Take care on administrative burden !! • don't ask for data which are in Government databases • assess the real usage of all collected data in time • cancel obligations of clients when are different ways to collect data</p>	<p>Centre.</p>	<p>public services Drafting and approving the methodology for drafting administrative regulations of public services B. Implementation of The National Action Plan for the implementation of the RM-EU Association Agreement 2014-2016 C. Implementation of Government of Moldova Activity Program 2015-2018 D. Implementation of Briefing book from Development Partners recommendations E. Use the relevant documents content of V4 countries provided in the Research embedded in the</p>
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		LPA cannot provide service in remote mode, the physical presence of the applicant at the mayor's office is required.				Digital Market		formally – publish them on the web, along with electronic version of the forms so that people could learn how to deal with their case. Transfer all the forms used in the office to active pdf (you may use tools like Scribus).			developed/amended documents
Lack of networking (IS) between raions (LPAII) and villages (LPAI)											
Decisional transparency/ lack of information										LPA Webpage	

Specific chapters for internal planning:

8. The main steps to be included into the Action plan for implementation of local e-services in rural localities (with a focus on legal regulations)

Poland Proposal

1. Sandbox stage – stage at which different approaches are tested. Provision of basic IT infrastructure, tuition and scholarship is a must
2. Recapitulation of gathered experience and formulation of guidelines and strategies throughout Moldova
3. Turning guidelines into regulations – attaching moneys and resources.

Slovakia proposal

1. To know and further watch development of EU legislation in areas of e-Government and digital agenda.
2. To initialize survey of needs for e-Services and look for proposals asked by general public (covering solution of all basic problems of technical character, as well as gaps in education etc.)

8.1. Consolidated main steps to be included into the Action plan - conclusions

To succeed in implementation of ICT based services at local level the country-wide approach is necessary to be applied.

The best practices from V4 countries provided in the present paper have to be additionally analysed through the already planned actions in the existing documents in the Republic of Moldova.

There are two most appropriate and relevant documents in Moldova in this regard: the Public Services Reform Program and The National Action Plan for the implementation of the RM-EU Association Agreement 2014-2016 . A majority of the recommended by V4 experts documents to be developed are covered by these 2 documents. Additional analysis should be undertaken to ensure uptake of best V4 practices at the local level, explained in an understandable, simple mode for the newly elected public servants to make possible providing contribution to transposed EU legislation in national legislation.

Awareness actions and the training of local public servants to ensure active involvement of local authorities in the decision making process will provide for the successful implementation of local ICT based services.

One of the most important activities would be the participation of local representatives in the discussions (under the DISCUS platform umbrella) of the draft documents to be developed according to the Public Services Reform Program and to the National Action Plan for the implementation of the RM-EU Association Agreement 2014-2016 (as soon as they will be published on www.particip.gov.md):

- law on public services
- law on archiving of electronic documents

- the methodology for the re-engineering of public services
- the framework methodology for setting tariffs for public services rendered against payment
- public policy proposal on centres for universal public services
- the methodology for drafting administrative regulations for public services
- the Government decision on government notification service (MNotify)
- the Government decision on government delivery service (MDelivery)
- the Government decision on the organization and functioning of the electronic document management information and records (SIGEDIA)
- the methodology for default digitization of public services
- amendments to the Regulation on single government portal content management of public services in connection with the development of the updated version (V2.0) of www.servicii.gov.md portal, and integration of electronic public services portal
- regulations and procedures for access and use of interoperability platform
- draft Government Decision “On state Register of local authorities Regulations”
- undertaking of annual surveys on most necessary ICT based services
- all other planned EU aquis documents, relevant to Information Society development.

Unfortunately, there is no document specifying what technical standards are necessary to be accepted and when will these be introduced .

9. Recommendations & suggestions for the next DISCUS event: Workshop planned for September 22-23, in Chisinau

Slovak Expert opinion:

- we need to focus more both on project outputs and common practical work of participants and Moldovan experts with support of V4 experts, so the workshop agenda of should be prepared following this approach
- we should spend time with information about DISCUS platform state of development of, how it will work, when will the testing phase open, how it will be promoted, how interesting persons could use it, who will be behind the scene to ensure the sustainability of the DISCUS platform etc.

Because V4 experts, brought and wrote a lot of information and to avoid unnecessary repetition, for the 2nd period of project it is feasible to focus on understanding of provided recommendations and higher involvement of people from Moldova into the project, through the following means:

- rewriting information from V4 experts contributions according to Moldovan local environment by Moldovan experts and participants of the second workshop and seminar before both events; they should take into account the current state and plans in e-Transformation project;

- initiate discussions about the views of people from the local government from Moldova (events' participants) between themselves and with the support of Moldovan and V4 experts to strive for real ways and actions;
- V4 experts will offer their opinion/feedback about understanding, procedures, ISs and e-Services proposed – it is necessary to activate people to develop things, based on the local conditions and on their own needs and perception;
- it will bring more active participation and more focused project outputs, therefore leading to a more clear view of pre-conditions for further project;
- it is necessary to prepare the environment for project sustainability – DISCUS platform, active people, etc.
- collecting opinions of people regarding the help they wish to receive from V4 countries experts (not only within this project, but also later – it could serve as a good basis for preparing additional projects based on real needs and move things forward this way)

Based on V4 experts materials and opinions, as well as the content of the Study research “Recommendation on implementation of relevant IS for local authorities” resulting from the first DISCUS workshop, the following recommendations for the preparation work and the agenda of September workshop are considered to be relevant:

Actions to be undertaken before the workshop:

Send email to all participants to DISCUS events and beyond, asking to access and read the published DISCUS materials and to make proposal for workshop discussions.

Send the Study Research I and II to the relevant Central Public authorities: Ministry of ICT, e-Government Centre, etc. and all LPA at raion level.

Collect from the participants in previous events, LPA representatives' Intention for Participation (according to the prepared Form), in the contest of draft Action Plans for their localities, to implement the ICT based services.

Pre-selection of best proposals (4 preselected LPAs)

Preparation of evaluation criteria for the selection of 2 LPAs for finalization of Action Plans

Proposals for the Agenda:

1. Presentation of the Research Study II (Dr. A. Gremalschi)
 - a. Discussions
 - b. Conclusions
2. Presentation(s) on lessons learnt from the Study visit in Poland (Ms. A. Stefanita, smbd else - tbd)
 - a. Proposals
 - b. Discussions
3. Presentation of the Action Plan template for LPA to be developed within the workshop.
4. Brainstorming on drafting the Action Plans for 4 preselected LPAs under the supervision of V4 experts (4 working groups)

5. Presentation of each developed Action Plan
6. Analysis of the presented Action Plans
7. Selection of 2 best Action Plans by the Evaluation committee elected before the start of brainstorming
8. Workshop Conclusions and recommendations

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ANNEX 1. List of normative acts that concerns to online public services (Republic of Moldova)

Laws:

1. Law Nr. 436-XVI of 28.12.2006 on Local Public Administration
2. Law no. 171-XIII of 6 July 1994 on commercial secret;
3. Law no. 982-XIV of 11 May 2000 regarding access to information;
4. Law no. 245-XVI of 27 November 2008 on the state secret;
5. Law no. 133 of 8 July 2011 on the protection of personal data;
6. Law no. 305 of 26 December 2012 on the reuse of public sector information;
7. Law no. 1069-XIV of 22 June 2000 on informatics;
8. Law no. 467-XV of 21 November 2003 on Information and State Information Resources;
9. Law nr. 71- XVI of 22.03.2007 on registers
10. Law no. 91 of 27 June 2014 on electronic signature and electronic document;

Government Decisions:

1. GOVERNMENT DECISION No. 1123 of 14 December 2010 "On Approval of Requirements for the assurance of personal data security at their processing within the information systems of personal data";
2. GOVERNMENT DECISION No. 710 of 20 September 2011 "On approval of the Strategic Program for technological modernization of governance (e-Transformation)";
3. GOVERNMENT DECISION No. 886 of November 8, 2013 "On approval of Methodological Norms for the application of Law no. 305 of 26 December 2012 on the reuse of public sector information ".
4. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 280 of 04.24.2013 regarding certain actions implementing the Government Electronic Payments Service (MPay) ·
5. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 719 of 16.09.2013 on Public Institution "Centre for Electronic Governance (E-Government)"
6. GOVERNMENT DECISION No. 857 of 31 October 2013 "On the National Strategy for Information Society Development" Digital Moldova 2020.
7. GOVERNMENT DECISION No. 122 of 18.02.2014, on public service reform program for the years 2014-2016.
8. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 886 of 11.08.2013 approving the Methodological Norms for the application of Law no. 305 of 26 December 2012 on the reuse of public sector information
9. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 1090, of 31.12.2013, the e-government services and access control authentication (MPass)

10. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 1096 of 31.12.2013 on the approval of the 2014 Action Plan to implement the Strategic Program for technological modernization of governance (e-Transformation)
11. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 122 of 18.02.2014 "On public services reform program for the years 2014-2016"
12. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 128 of 20.02.2014 on common government technological platform (MCloud)
13. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 405 of 06/02/2014 on e-government services integrated digital signature (MSign)
14. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 461 of 16/06/2014 amending and supplementing Government Decision no. 294 of March 17, 1998
15. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 700 of 08.25.2014 on publishing open government data
16. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 404 of 02.06.2014 on piloting interoperability platform
17. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 701 of 08.25.2014 on approval of published open government data Methodology
18. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 708 of 28.08.2014 on e-government services log (Mlog)
19. GOVERNMENT DECISION Nr. 717 of 29.08.2014 on the platform of permits and registers (PGRAP)
20. Order no. 305 of 09.09.2014 on approval of Agreement Contract model type and on provision of shared government technology platform (MCloud)

ANNEX 2. EU legislation with direct impact information society (ordered by date of relevance):

- Directive 96/9/EC of 11.3.1996 on the legal protection of databases
- Directive 1999/93/EC of 13.12.1999 on a Community framework for electronic signatures
- Directive 2000/31/EC of 8.5.2000 on eCommerce
- Regulation 2002/733/EC of 22.4.2002 on the implementation of the .eu Top Level Domain
- Directive 2002/58/EC from 12.7.2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications)
- Council Framework Decision 2005/222/JHA of 24 February 2005 on attacks against information systems
- Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2007 establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE)
- Decision of Council and EP 922/2009/EC on 16.9.2009 on interoperability solutions for European public administrations (ISA)
- Opinion of the European Data Protection Supervisor on Promoting Trust in the Information Society by Fostering Data Protection and Privacy (2010/C 280/01)
- Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC
- Directive 2002/22/EC of 7.3.2002 on universal service
- Directive 2003/98/EC of 17.11.2003 on reuse of public sector information (PSI)
- Directive 2006/123/EC from 12.12.2006 on services in the internal market
- Regulation 2009/767/EC on the placing on the market and use of feed by which are setting arrangements for simplification of procedures by “places of unique contacts”
- Regulation 2011/130/EU which are setting minimal requirements on cross border processing of documents electronically signed by bodies
- Directive 2008/114/EC of 8.12.2008 on identification and labelling of European critical infrastructures and about appreciation of improvement of its protection
- Directive 2011/92/EU of 13.2.2011 on actions against sex imposition and sex exploitation of children and against children pornography

ANNEX 3. Fact sheet DISCUS #3-June 2015 and information on Seminar

DISCUS Scientific seminar: ICT solutions for local services (legal regulations)		26-27 may 2015 Chişinău
over 50 participants 		
25 local public representatives		
Representatives of:		
- civil society 		
Research study Ro & Eng 		

Information on the Seminar

(<http://www.discus.idsi.md/seminar-May-26-27>)

On **26-27 May in Chisinau** took place the second event of the **DISCUS project** – Discussion on Information Society Building Issues Platform. It was organized a **scientific seminar** with the topic: **ICT solutions for local services (legal regulations)**. Were received around **35 application forms** for participation from local public representatives from various districts of the country. There were invited about **15 speakers** from Moldova and Visegrad countries.

The event was attended by approx. **50 people** - specialists in various areas: local public servants, representatives of academic sector, central government, civil society, national experts and international experts from Visegrad countries.

The **main purpose** of the event was to share experience of Visegrad countries in the field of information society with a focus on legal regulations in the field of electronic services including local and taking into consideration the best practices in this area Visegrad countries by the moldovan officials, researchers and national policy makers. The **objective of the seminar** was to discuss problems and to identify possible solutions for legal regulations for local electronic services in Moldova.

The seminar was opened by the representative of the [Academy of Sciences](#) - Dr.hab. Veaceslav Ursachi coordinator of Engineering Sciences and Technology Section of ASM. With a word of greeting came the director of [Information Society Development Institute](#) -Dr. Igor Cojocaru and Deputy Head of the Department of Information Technology Policies, [Ministry of Information and Communication Technology](#) - Andrei Cușcă.

Professor, dr.hab. Anatol Gremalschi, Program director at Public Policy Institute presented the study conducted by the DISCUS experts based on the Ist DISCUS workshop from 17-18 March, which had the topic: ICT-driven local development.

Andrei Cușcă, Deputy Head of the Department of Information Technology Policies, [Ministry of Information and Communication Technology](#) has presented the National Strategy "Digital Moldova 2020" - the basic policy document on development of information society in Moldova.

Igor Cernei, specialist in information technologies, Orhei City Hall presented the case study: Center for Information and Services of Orhei City Hall and the Geographic Information System Orhei.

Petru Culeac, Community Mobilization Consultant, [USAID Local Government Support Project in Moldova](#) talked about Development and institutionalization of effective communication with citizens instruments (1.0 WebAPL platform).

The key-speakers of the event were 3 experts from Visegrad countries: dr. Krzysztof Atlasiewicz from Poland; Ing. Vladimir Benko - Slovakia; RNDr. Datel Vratislav from Czech Republic.

Krzysztof Atlasiewicz presented useful information and advices for ICT strategic planning by local authorities. Vladimir Benko spoke about the model of open self-government of Presov – systematic and effective building of info services and on the second day of the seminar presented ICT tools for environmental management at local level, issuing several recommendations to Moldova. Vratislav Datel talked about legislation and technical standards in Public Administration.

Eduard Fricățel, legal consultant and Vlad Manoil, specialist of the Center for Electronic Governance presented the legal framework for Governance Agenda eTransformation, respectively eGovernment platforms implemented for central public authorities and available for reuse by local authorities.

The event ended with a communication about interoperability as an opportunity to modernize local services presented by PhD Mihai Grecu, Head of Laboratory at the Information Society Development Institute.

DISCUS - scientific seminar participants showed interested to the subject of e-services at the local level, focusing on legal regulations, acknowledging the importance of technology in all areas of public life.

According to the final evaluation questionnaires completed by participants of the seminar from May 26-27, the majority were very satisfied or satisfied with the organization of the event. 100% of participants would recommend the seminar to colleagues for participation.

DISCUS project team of the Information Society Development Institute thank all speakers, moderators and participants at the second event DISCUS!

Presentations from the event are available here:

- **National Strategy "Digital Moldova 2020"** - Deputy Head of the Department of Information Technology Policies, [Ministry of Information and Communication Technology](#)

- **Presentation on research study based on findings of the DISCUS workshop from march 2015** - dr. hab. Anatol Gremalschi, Program director, Public Policy Institute

- **Study**

case:Center for Information and Services of Orhei City Hall and the Geographic Information System Orhei - Igor Cernei, Orhei

- **Development and institutionalization of effective communication with citizens**

instruments - Petru Culeac, consultant mobilizare comunitară, [USAID Local Government Support Project in Moldova](#)

- **Interoperability - as an opportunity to modernize local services** - Mihai Grecu, Information Society Development Institute

- **Open self-government: city Presov** - Ing. Vladimir Benko, Slovakia

- **ICT tools for environment management for local authorities** - Ing. Vladimir Benko, Slovakia

- **ICT strategic planning by local authorities - I part** - dr. Krysztof Atlasiewicz, Poland

- **ICT strategic planning by local authorities - II part** - dr. Krysztof Atlasiewicz, Poland

- **Legislation and technical standards - I part** - RNDr. Datel Vratislav, Czech Republic

- **Legislation and technical standards - II part** - RNDr. Datel Vratislav, Czech Republic

Photo gallery from the event!

ANNEX 4. Seminar Agenda

Agenda

Scientific Seminar: ICT solutions for Local Services (legal regulations)

26 - 27.05.2015 - Chişinău, Moldova

Labour Institute, Room no. 6, Zimbrului 10 str. , Chişinău - 2024, Moldova

1 st Day - May 26 th			
Time	nr	Topic/presentation	Speaker/expert/moderator
9.00 - 09.30	Arrival & Registration		
	1	Seminar opening	Igor Cojocaru, IDSI (M)
09.30 - 09.40	1.1	Opening remarks & overview of the Agenda	Igor Cojocaru Director, Information Society Development Institute
09.45- 09.55	1.2	Welcome speech	Acad. Gheorghe Duca , president of the Academy of Science of Moldova
10.00 - 10.10	1.3	Welcome speech	Andrei Cuşcă , Ministry of Information Technology and Communications
10.15 - 10.25	1.4	Welcome speech from the diplomatic corps of the Visegrad countries in Chisinau	
10.25 - 10.30	1.5	Welcome speech	Ceauş Sergiu , Deputy General Secretary of the Government
10.30 - 10.45	1.6	Presentation of the 1 st project study research	Anatol Gremalschi , Program director Institute for Public Policy (IPP)
	2	National Legal Regulations on ICT in Local Public Administration	Ion Coşuleanu, ISDI
10.55 - 11.20	2.1	National strategy "Digital Moldova 2020" - a basic policy document on development of the information society in Moldova	Andrei Cuşcă , Deputy Head, Department of Information Technology policies, the Ministry of Information Technology and Communications
11.25 - 11.55		Discussions & Coffee Break	
12.00 - 12.30	2.2	The legal framework for the e-Transformation Agenda of the Governance	Eduard Fricatel , Legal Consultant, Center for Electronic Governance
12.35 - 13.05	2.3	Center for Information and Services of Orhei City Hall and the Geographic Information System Orhei	Igor Cernei , Specialist City Hall Orhei
13.10 - 13.55		Lunch	
14.00 - 14.25	2.4	Development and institutionalization of effective communication with citizens instruments (1.0 WebAPL platform)	Petru Culeac , Community Mobilization Consultant, USAID Local Government Support Project in Moldova

	3	Good V4 countries practices	Anatol Gremalschi , Program director Institute for Public Policy
14.30 - 15.00	3.1	Information Technology Strategic Planning by local authorities (Part I)	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert from Poland
15.05 - 15.35	3.2	Open self-government: City Presov - systematic and effective building of info services	Vladimir Benko Expert from Slovakia
15.40 - 16.10	3.3	Legislation and technical standards in Public Administration (part I)	Vratislav Datel Expert from Czech Republic
16.15 - 16.50		Coffee Break	
	4	e-Government platforms in Moldova	Ion Coşuleanu, ISDI
16.55 - 18.20	4.1	e-Government platforms, implemented for central public authorities and available for reuse by local authorities	Iurie Țurcanu, Chief Technological Coordinator, Deputy Director Center for Electronic Governance
18.20 - 18.30	4.2	Final discussions & conclusions	Anatol Gremalschi - IPP Ion Coşuleanu - ISDI
18.30 - 19.30	Networking event		
2nd Day – 27 May			
	5	Good V4 countries practices	Mihai GreCu, IDSI (M)
09.00 - 09.30	5.1	Legislation and technical standards in Public Administration (part II)	Vratislav Datel Expert from Czech Republic
09.35 - 10.05	5.2	Information Technology Strategic Planning by local authorities (Part II)	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert from Poland
10.10 - 10.40	5.3	ICT tools for environment management for local authorities - recommendations for Moldova	Vladimir Benko Expert from Slovakia
10.40 - 11.00		Q&A session	
11.00 - 11.45		Coffee Break	
11.50 - 12.20	6.1	Interoperability - an opportunity to modernize local public services	Mihai GreCu, IDSI
12.20 - 12.45		Final discussions & conclusions of the event	
12.50 - 13.20		Handing participation certificates	
13.20 - 13.30		Feedback questionnaire & final organisational issues	
13.30 - 14.10	Lunch		
14.10 - 14.30	Wrap-up & Departure		

DISCUS is a project coordinated by the [Information Society Development Institute](#),
funded under the [International Visegrad Fund](#)

ANNEX 5. Excerpts from the Government of the Republic of Moldova Activity Program 2015-2018

Information society, information technology and communications

6. Create conditions for the development and exploitation of national digital content.

7. Enhancing digital literacy, skills and digital inclusion development. Increasing security and trust in the digital space.

10. Adjustment of the normative-legal base for implementing government Interoperability Framework and of recommendations on interconnection and interoperability of content / indigenous resources.

Implementation of access to registers and databases of national importance for all central and local public authorities and institutions in accordance with the duties and functions of these authorities.

11. Coordinate the creation of automated information systems, with re-engineering the processes of existing public service with the purpose of rendering them electronically. Implementation of electronic document and facilitate full use of digital signatures to request and provide of all public services provided by the central authorities.

Public services Reform

1. Continues elimination of outdated and inefficient public services and offering online and mobile public services system for all citizens and business .

2. Development of e-Government platform and of a national electronic system.

3. Introduction of electronic voting and encourage forms of participative democracy through computer systems, including distance voting to ensure the involvement of the diaspora in domestic social-political processes.

4. Implementation of interoperability framework for State information systems .

5. Implementation of unique system of electronic circulation of documents within central public authorities.

6. Implementation and ensuring functionality of the government portal of electronic public services.

7. Develop and implement administrative regulations determining modality of electronic public services provision.

8. Departmental data center consolidation and development of common government technological platform (MCloud) in accordance with international standards.

9. Promoting smart investments in IT in the central government.

ANNEX 6. Participants Brief Proposals at the end of Seminar

Localities proposed by participants themselves for development of draft action plans for implementation of local e-services (in 2 rural localities - based on project proposal)

Lipcani, Briceni
Ialoveni
Ocnița
Sărata Veche

Participants proposals:

Orhei:

- more similar events
- the problem is that the stakeholders of e-government process do not interact among them

ISDI - A.Rusu

- the process should be from bottom to up - as Orhei case
- the government should adopt laws that allow local authorities to manage by themselves all issues at the local level
- there are still a lot barriers in issuing certificates - for ex. CTS is a monopolistic governmental structure

Ialoveni - Igor Plamadeala

- direct collaboration agreements among different authorities/stakeholders can be more efficient than Government Decision or other official documents

Balti:

- such a training should be provided to entrepreneurs. Business sector is an important partner for local authorities. Today APL are very distant from business, but they represent a market sector for business.

Ocnita:

- concrete actions are necessary - a product, not only discussions

A mayor:

- waiting for an economical result - e.g..tTo save paper etc., increase security

Truseni:

- there were a tentative to implement something, but is necessary at the central level and to have a group of experts (for fields: cadastre, registers, personal data etc.)

Vatra:

- Local authorities are the main/biggest data providers but at the same time they to not have access to these data

K. Atlasiewicz

- a stocktaking of all public authorities possessions is necessary (in terms in ICT, information systems etc.)

V. Benko

- Moldova has good strategies but there is a lack of finance for a better implementation of all plans, documents

V. Datel:

- technical standards are important

A.Gremalschi

- process re-engineering
- planning money for ICT in local budget
- bottomup approach
- local servants should manifest initiative and wish
- enabling regional development
- political will and decision are very important

Participants proposals:

- information campaigns
- a pilot project from the central level to raion - and from raion to cities/villages
- study visits in Visegrad countries
- all DISCUS materials are very useful to be published and disseminated
- it is necessary to impose the change, otherwise in Moldova is not possible to implement a good e-Government process in the entire country
- to avoid documents duplication
- at the end on June - the DISCUS team will visit Comrat - Gagauzia - P. Veaceslav
- there is need of more trainings and raising awareness
- to create a group of experts who would consult and support local authorities
- it is important that the presented information is delivered to officials, too
- to involve the citizens more in DISCUS studies, to collaborate with the civil society
- to build a partnership network (central government, local, civil society, business etc.)
- to organise such seminars at the local level - it is something new